

Acknowledgement

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References

1. V. M. RAO, V. ANANTA RAMAM, and M. N. SASTRI, *Curr. Sci.*, 1976, 45, 451.
2. N. R. ANIFINDI, V. M. RAO and V. ANANTA RAMAM, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, 15A, 561.
3. T. SPINNER and G. M. HARRIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, 11, 1067.
4. KEITH J. LAIDLER, "Chemical Kinetics" Ch. 1. McGraw Hill, II Ed., 1965, p. 16.
5. R. F. JAMESON and J. E. SALMON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 360.

Viscosity Variations in Non-ideal Homogeneous Binary Liquid Mixtures of Non-electrolytes

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THE existence of new species in non-ideal homogeneous binary liquid mixtures of non-electrolytes have been predicted from viscosity measurements by various workers^{1,2} in the past. Recently, the authors in an earlier publication³ explained the occurrence of maxima or minima in the excess viscosity η^E versus composition plots of a few such systems by assuming the existence of mobile liquid structures having a central molecule of one component surrounded by the molecules of the other component. It was considered desirable to test the applicability of the authors' earlier conclusions further by considering some more systems in the hope to understand the deviations from ideal viscometric behaviour in terms of the molecular and bulk properties of the pure components.

Results and Discussion

In a homogeneous binary liquid mixture of components A and B, A provides the central molecule in corresponding liquid structures if $(X_A)_{max} \leq 0.5$ and surrounding molecules if $(X_A)_{max} \geq 0.5$ while either of the two situations are equally possible if $(X_A)_{max} = 0.5$, where $(X_A)_{max}$ the mole fraction of component A corresponds to $(\eta^E)_{max}$, the maximum excess viscosity of the binary³. Also for polar-polar and polar-apolar binaries, $\eta^E = +ve$ when $(\mu_c - \mu_s) = +ve$ and $\eta^E = -ve$ when $(\mu_c - \mu_s) = -ve$ where μ_c and μ_s are the dipole moments of the molecules of the central and surrounding components respectively forming the mobile liquid structures. On the other hand, for apolar-apolar

binaries, $\eta^E = +ve$ or $-ve$ according as the central molecule in the mobile liquid structures increases or decreases orientation in the mixture.

In order to verify the above conclusions, the viscosity of various binary liquid mixtures of non-electrolytes at 25° and varying compositions were taken from published data⁴ and the excess viscosity η^E was calculated⁵ and plotted against X_A for each system. A close look at the curves so obtained made them to be grouped in three categories: (i) curves showing maxima alone, (ii) curves showing minima alone, and (iii) curves showing maxima and minima both. One typical curve from each category is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Plots of excess viscosity (η^E) versus mole fraction (X_A) for binary mixtures at 25°C of (I) CCl_4 (A) + CH_3OH (B) showing maxima alone, (II) $\text{CH}_2\text{CO-CH}_3$ (A) + $\eta\text{-C}_6\text{H}_7\text{CO}_2\text{H}$ (B) showing minima alone, & (III) CCl_4 (A) + $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ (B) showing maxima and minima both.

For every system considered, the value of $(X_A)_{max}$ and the corresponding value of $(\eta^E)_{max}$ were obtained from the maxima/minima in the respective plots of η^E vs X_A . Further, the type of the central as well as the surrounding component and the sign of $(\mu_c - \mu_s)$ for polar-polar as well as polar-apolar binaries and orienting tendency of the central molecule of corresponding mobile liquid structure in apolar-apolar binaries were predicted by applying the above conditions. The results are tabulated in Table 1.

A close observation of table 1 indicates that for systems 1 to 17, the predicted sign of $(\mu_c - \mu_s)$ tallies with the calculated sign as required. However, for the

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TABLE 1—VALUES OF $(X_A)_{max}$, $(\eta^E)_{max}$ AND COMPARATIVE SIGNS OF $(\mu_c - \mu_s)$ OR ORIENTING TENDENCIES OF THE COMPONENT MOLECULES IN NON-IDEAL BINARY LIQUID SYSTEMS.

Sl. No.	Component (A)	System Component (B)	$(X_A)_{max}$ at 25° C	$(\eta^E)_{max}$ at 25° C	Component providing central molecule	Component providing surrounding molecule	Predicted Sign of $(\mu_c - \mu_s)$ for polar-polar and polar-apolar systems and orienting tendency of central molecule for apolar-apolar systems
1.	C ₆ H ₆	CCl ₄	0.53	-0.0102	B	A	Less orienting
2.	C ₆ H ₆	CS ₂	0.09 0.52	-0.0028 0.0068	A B	B A	Less orienting orienting
3.*	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₃	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃) ₂	0.46 0.82	-0.0270 0.0750	A B	B A	- ve + ve
4.*	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₃	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃) ₂	0.73	-0.0057	B	A	- ve
5.*	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅ Cl	0.45 0.80	-0.0004 0.0002	A B	B A	- ve + ve
6.*	C ₆ H ₅ Cl	C ₆ H ₅ I	0.53	-0.0190	B	A	- ve
7.	C ₆ H ₁₁	CCl ₄	0.50	-0.0375	A or B	B or A	Less orienting
8.	CH ₃ COCH ₃	CH ₃ CO ₂ H	0.55	-0.1040	B	A	- ve
9.	CH ₃ COCH ₃	<i>n</i> -C ₇ H ₇ CO ₂ H	0.60	-0.1090	B	A	- ve
10.	CH ₃ COC ₂ H ₅	<i>n</i> -C ₇ H ₅ CO ₂ H	0.52	-0.1070	B	A	- ve
11.	C ₂ H ₅ OC ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅ OH	0.43	-0.2900	A	B	- ve
12.	C ₄ H ₈ O ₂	C ₂ H ₅ OH	0.42	-0.2520	A	B	- ve
13.	C ₄ H ₈ O ₂	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉ OH	0.35	-0.6850	A	B	- ve
14.	C ₄ H ₈ O ₂	<i>iso</i> -C ₄ H ₉ OH	0.33	-1.1800	A	B	- ve
15.	C ₄ H ₈ O ₂	<i>sec</i> -C ₄ H ₉ OH	0.30	-1.0800	A	B	- ve
16.	C ₄ H ₈ O ₂	<i>tert</i> -C ₄ H ₉ OH	0.24	-2.2000	A	B	- ve
17.	CCl ₄	<i>iso</i> -C ₇ H ₇ OH	0.48	-0.4400	A	B	- ve
18.	CCl ₄	CH ₃ OH	0.36	0.1260	A	B	- ve
19.	CCl ₄	C ₂ H ₅ OH	0.13 0.81	0.0220 -0.0390	A B	B A	- ve + ve
20.	CCl ₄	<i>n</i> -C ₇ H ₇ OH	0.34 0.88	0.1120 -0.0680	A B	B A	- ve + ve

* Values are at 20 °C

systems 18 to 20 the predicted sign of $(\mu_c - \mu_s)$ is opposite to the calculated sign. It is interesting to note that in all these deviating binaries, one component is a small apolar molecule while the other is a lower alcohol with strong hydrogen bonding. In such cases, the mixing occurs mainly by the combined effect of the two competing processes: (i) interstitial accommodation of the apolar molecule in the association matrix of the alcohol increasing orientation and (ii) the diluent action of the apolar molecule upsetting the association matrix and consequently decreasing

orientation. Accordingly, in the case of CCl₄ - CH₃OH binary, the strongly hydrogen bonded CH₃OH molecules with small alkyl chain give rise to a stable association matrix which conveniently accommodates the CCl₄ molecules throughout the composition range. The overall effect is an increased order giving positive η^E with CCl₄ molecules in the centre surrounded by the CH₃OH molecules of the association matrix. This conclusion is corroborated by the existence of a maxima in η^E vs composition curve with positive $(\eta^E)_{max}$ at $(X_A)_{max} < 0.5$.

In the cases of $\text{CCl}_4 - \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ and $\text{CCl}_4 - n - \text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}$ binaries, the alkyl chains are comparatively longer and the alcohol molecules are comparatively less strongly hydrogen bonded than in the case of $\text{CCl}_4 - \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ binary. The association matrix, though strong enough to accommodate the CCl_4 molecules in alcohol rich mixtures, becomes less efficient in alcohol poor mixtures and ultimately breaks down due to dielectric effects of CCl_4 which then acts as diluent. Thus, in alcohol rich mixtures, the order is enhanced giving +ve η^E with CCl_4 molecules in the centre surrounded by alcohol molecules. While in the alcohol poor mixtures, the order is decreased giving -ve η^E with alcohol molecules in the centre surrounded by CCl_4 molecules. This explains the occurrence of a +ve $(\eta^E)_{max}$ with $(X_A)_{max} < 0.5$ in the alcohol rich mixtures together with a -ve $(\eta^E)_{max}$ with $(X_A)_{max} > 0.5$ in alcohol poor mixtures for each of the two cases considered. On the other hand in the case of $\text{CCl}_4 - \text{iso-C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}$ binary, the alkyl chain is longer and branched. Moreover, the alcohol concerned is still less hydrogen bonded than in the cases discussed earlier. Consequently, the association matrix is weak and unable to accommodate the CCl_4 molecules which in effect act as diluent throughout the composition range of the binary. As such η^E values are always negative with -ve $(\eta^E)_{max}$ at $(X_A)_{max} < 0.5$. This explanation is further substantiated by the behaviour of the systems 12 to 16 in Table 1.

Thus from the data of Table 1, the applicability of the conditions specified earlier is amply justified for the binary mixtures of polar-polar, polar-apolar and apolar-apolar components provided none of them is strongly associated; while the mixtures of small apolar molecules with lower alcohols having strong hydrogen bonding, deviate from the expected behaviour. However, the anomalous behaviour is explained on the consideration of the tendency of such apolar molecules to get accommodated in the association matrix of the corresponding alcohol in the binary.

References

1. R. J. FORT and W. R. MOORE, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1966, 62, 1112.
2. R. K. NIGAM and B. S. MAHL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 1255.
3. R. P. SINGH and S. S. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 790.
4. J. TIMMERMANS, "Physico-Chemical Constants of Binary Systems", Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1959, vol 1 & 2.
5. M. MODELL and R. C. REID, "Thermodynamics and its Applications", Prentice-Hall, Inc., Englewood Cliffs, N. J., 1974, p. 262.

Excess Volumes of Mixing of Some Electron Donating Hydrocarbons with an Electron Accepting Liquid Chlorobenzene

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IN continuation of our earlier studies on excess volumes of some polar and nonpolar liquids with N-methylacetamide (NMA)¹, Propylene carbonate (PC)², Dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO)³ and N,N'-Dimethylformamide (DMF)⁴, we have now extended the work on the binary mixtures of some electron donating hydrocarbons with highly electron accepting liquid chlorobenzene. We report excess volumes of chlorobenzene + cyclohexane, + benzene, + toluene, + xylene, and + mesitylene at 30°. In the present work the series of five hydrocarbons was selected because it was thought that electron donating power of hydrocarbons would increase down the series. Excess volumes of these hydrocarbons with hexafluorobenzene have been reported earlier⁵.

Experimental

Cyclohexane, xylene and mesitylene of A. R. grade were twice distilled and the middle fraction was collected. The procedure for purifying the other liquids and for measuring the excess volumes has been described elsewhere¹. The results obtained are summarised in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

It may be noted from Table 1 that excess volume of mixing V_m^E for all the five systems is negative over the entire concentration range. The negative values of V_m^E shows a stronger interaction between the components of the mixture. From the plots, the excess volume of mixing at equimolar concentration were calculated and these values are recorded in Table 2.

It is clear from Table 2 that V_m^E at a constant mole fraction decreases as the electron donating power of hydrocarbons increases. This shows that greater the difference in electronegativity of the components, greater is the interaction.

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